

VindKraftNet 15th April 2026

Welcome

Safety moment

- Alarms
 - There will be the weekly alarm test at 12:00 today
 - Listen out for other alarms
- Fire exits and muster point
- Toilet facilities

Sustenance

- Lunch is in the canteen in a neighbouring building
- A coffee, tea and cake is provided in the afternoon break

VindKraftNet 15th April 2026

Welcome

In numbers

Employees

471

452

Professors

20

19

PhD fellows

128

110

Researchers

59%

59%

Women

27%

25%

International background

58%

58%

2025

2024

Department Coordinators

Education - Joachim Holbøll
 Scientific Advise - Birte Holst Jørgensen
 Director of development - Peter Bagger Hjuler
 Test Centre Manager - Allan Vesth
 Innovation - Frida Frost

DTWO

EU HE

Coordinator
Xiaoli Guo Larsén

Offshore wind energy, digitally twinned for reliability

DTWO

Funded by
the European Union

Digital twin architecture for offshore wind power chain: from weather, with wind farm wakes, to siting, turbine operation, grid and energy system

frontiers | Frontiers in Energy Research

TYPE: Original Research
published: 22 August 2024
doi: 10.3389/ferg.2024.1404791

Check for updates

OPEN ACCESS

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University of Perugia, Italy

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Chinese Academy of Sciences (CAS), China
Igor Esau,
Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing

**The impact of
on extreme wi
Europe accord**

Xiaoli Guo Larsén*, Marc Imberger

Department of Wind and Energy Systems,

POLISH MARITIME RESEARCH 4 (128) 2025 Vol. 32; pp. 187-194
10.2478/pomr-2025-0061

**SCADA-Based Offshore Wind Turbine Monitoring:
A Review of Methods of Addressing Marine Environmental Challenges**

Klaudia Wzrak, Agata Kolakowska, Patryk Jasi, Paweł Szy, Jerzy Dębicki, Bogdan Wianiewicz, Gdańsk University of Technology, Poland

*Corresponding author: klawracz@poczta.gdansk.pl (K. Wzrak)

Boundary-Layer Meteorology (2025) 191:50
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10546-025-00942-9>

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Development of One-Way Coupling Between MIKE 3 Wave FM Model and WRF-LES for the Evaluation of a Storm Simulation

Sima Hamzeloo¹ · Xiaoli Guo Larsén¹ · Alfredo Peña¹ · Stephan Kistner² · Jacob Tornfeldt Sørensen²

journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/renene

ELSEVIER

Investigation of wind farm impacts on surface waves using coupled numerical simulations[†]

Xiaoli Guo Larsén^{a,*}, Jana Fischereit^a, Sima Hamzeloo^b, Konrad Bärfuss^b, Astrid Lampert^b

^a Department of Wind and Energy Systems, Technical University of Denmark, Frederiksborgvej 399, Roskilde, 4000, Denmark
^b Institute of Flight Guidance, Technische Universität Braunschweig, Braunschweig, 38106, Germany

<https://doi.org/10.5194/wes-2025-42>
Preprint. Discussion started: 2 April 2025
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Impact of atmospheric turbulence on performance and loads of wind turbines: Knowledge gaps and research challenges

Branko Kosović^{1,*}, Sukanta Basu^{2,*}, Jacob Berg³, Larry K. Berg⁴, Sue E. Haupt⁵, Xiaoli G. Larsén⁶, Joachim Peinke⁷, Richard J. A. M. Stevens⁸, Paul Veers⁹, and Simon Watson¹⁰

<https://doi.org/10.5194/wes-2025-245>
Preprint. Discussion started: 16 December 2025
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eawe | WIND ENERGY SCIENCE DISCUSSIONS

Modelling global offshore turbulence intensity including large-scale turbulence, stability and sea state

Xiaoli Guo Larsén¹, Marc Imberger¹, and Rogier Floors¹

¹Wind and Energy Systems Department, Technical University of Denmark, Frederiksborgvej 399, Roskilde, 4000, Denmark

EuroWindWakes

tems

CETP, EUDP

Coordinator, Berdhard Stoevesandt
DK Coordinator, Jake Badger

EuroWindWakes European Offshore Dataset

Fischereit, J., Vollmer, L., & Hansen, A. (2025). Open European offshore wind turbine database [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17311571>

PhDs in Resource Assessment and Meteorology

Keeta Chapman-Smith

Modelling Tropical Cyclones for Safer Farm Design and Operation

MSCA

Nicolas Gonzalez Alonso-de-Linaje

Wake modeling for large-scale wind farm cluster optimization

DFF MAMAS, EU HE WIMBY, DTU

Andreas Thorsen

Storms Over Offshore Wind Farms: Understanding and modelling the harsh conditions of offshore wind farms

DTU-Equinor Academic Collaboration

Agustí Porta Ko

Robust operation of AWE in low and high wind speed conditions

MSCA

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Good VindKraftNet Day

DTU

